

Nigeria Fellowship of Evangelical Students (NIFES)

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The Nigeria Fellowship of Evangelical Students (NIFES) is an interdenominational Christian movement established in 1968 to cater for the spiritual needs of Christian students in Nigeria's tertiary educational institutions. The body is affiliated to the International Fellowship of Evangelical Students (IFES) and is acclaimed to have affected several hundred lives across the nation. NIFES has established its unit fellowships on several campuses including Universities, Polytechnics and Colleges of Education spread across the six geo-political zones of the country. The group builds disciples, trains and explores the potentials in the young folks who choose to identify with them. NIFES prides itself as an organisation that is in the habit of building tomorrow's leaders today. NIFES focuses on evangelism and discipleship. They do this by encouraging members to take part in programmes geared towards soul-winning and disciple-building. At the apex of the group's organogram is a Board of Trustees which includes eminent personalities in the nation's Christian circle. The group is led by a National Director who coordinates the day-to-day activities of the organization. NIFES is structured into sub-zones and zones for easy administration. Each zone is coordinated by the Training Secretary who constantly visits campuses in their area ensuring they keep up with the ministry's cardinal programmes at all times. Each NIFES campus unit is governed by a student executive council elected by the local congregation under the supervision of the Training Secretary. Due to the nature of the group, it is necessary to have change of student executive yearly. This is because while some graduate, others would need to change executive positions and serve in other roles before they also exit the campus at their own time. The campus/unit Executive report to the Training Secretary who in turn makes report of the campus fellowships in their area to the regional/national leadership. They hold national programmes at the NIFES National Campgrounds in Kwali, in the outskirts of Abuja, Nigeria's Federal Capital Territory. To meet her financial obligations, the fellowship relies on funding received from offertory collections taken during fellowship meetings as well as from friends, patrons and other free-will offerings from other categories of people. Since the fellowship was one of the first campus Christian groups to appear in Nigeria, it has served generations of students for close to six decades. Many old-time members of the group recommend them to their children, wards, relations and friends who are newly admitted to Nigerian tertiary educational institutions. As a result, the fellowship thrives on a reputation and standard it has built over the years.

Date Range: 1968 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Region tags: Nigeria, Africa

Nigeria, West Africa. Most Nigerian Pentecostals live in southern Nigeria.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: God's Response to Nigeria: The Story of NIFES by Simeon E. Ifere

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: www.nifes.org.ng

– Source 1 Description: NIFES official website

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.kingjamesbibleonline.org/>

– Source 1 Description: The King James Version of the Holy Bible

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: Since the group is an interdenominational Christian body, it interacts with all students who identify with it as their members are drawn from different Christian denominations across the country. All the patrons of the fellowship are also members of different Christian groups across the country. The group interacts with these churches in driving her vision and mission.

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: The cultural contact is competitive in the sense that many religious groups in most parts of Nigeria seek to attract more residents of the country to their fold. They all go about trying to recruit membership from the same population.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: The cultural contact the group has with other religious groups is accommodating. Since the country is a multi-religious state, the group maintains a peaceful relationship with other religious groups found in the country.

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

Notes: The answer to this question is a little bit complicated. This is so because while the religious group is neutral to some other groups which share its ideologies and beliefs, and so is comfortable with their members continuing in such religious groups, it seeks to convert others who belong to groups it considers not to uphold the principles it views as acceptable to the supreme being to its fold.

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: Violent conflicts have been reported in some northern States of Nigeria where the group is found. In most of these cases of violence, the group has been unfortunate to have been victims of attacks. They do not have the custom of perpetrating violence but have been victims of much violence in the affected regions of the country. They have however been well accommodated in most southern states of the country.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Notes: The group does not have a tradition of perpetrating violence either within or outside the sample region.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

Notes: To belong to the fellowship, a member must first be a student of any of the higher institutions of learning in Nigeria where a branch of the fellowship is found.

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

Notes: To become a member of the fellowship, one must first be a student of an institution of higher learning in Nigeria. Membership of the fellowship is therefore not assigned at birth.

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: It is assigned by the personal choice/decision of students of any tertiary educational institution in Nigeria

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– No

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: The group engages in evangelistic campaigns with the motive of recruiting new members to their fold.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

Notes: Proselytizing is mandated for their religious professionals. This is so because proselytising is one of the major ways of recruiting members into the group. Proselytising is therefore highly emphasised and encouraged among them.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– No

Notes: It is not mandated but is highly emphasised and encouraged among them.

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

Notes: Missionary work is mandated for the religious professionals in the group. Their missionary efforts usually take the form of establishing more campus fellowships and organising training programmes for members and student leaders across fellowships in order to keep the vision of the group alive and to ensure the students run with the vision for the growth of the group.

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– No

Notes: Though missionary work is not mandated for members, it is highly recommended and encouraged among them. The group holds that their growth is highly dependent on the success of their missionary efforts.

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– No

Notes: The group does not employ coercion in membership recruitment.

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: The group has no official political support.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Notes: The group believes that members who depart from them may be restored with prayers. They keep the doors of reconciliation open to such members as they continue to pray for their restoration.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 2200000

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 1.5

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (one of many small religious groups in sample region)

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The group has recognised leaders who are elected to serve in various capacities for a pre-determined period of time as provided for in their constitution.

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

Notes: There is a hierarchy among the leaders of the group. While each fellowship is led by elected student executives, the group is coordinated centrally or nationally by older Christian workers. There are Training Secretaries (TS) who coordinate the activities of a small number of campus fellowships. They are further responsible to the Area Directors (AD) who are in turn responsible to the National Officers.

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– No

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– Yes

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Yes

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:

– Number of levels [numeric value]: 5

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– No

Notes: The group does not ascribe supernatural powers to their leaders. However, they are believed to be capable of performing special spiritual activities as permitted by the supreme being.

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

Notes: Student members choose their fellowship leaders while the national officers also determine their succession procedures.

↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:

– No

Notes: The task of leadership succession is usually undertaken by the group as a whole. It is not the responsibility of the leader alone.

↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:

– No

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:

– Yes

↳ A political leader chooses the leader:

– No

Notes: Political leaders do not get involved in leadership succession in the fellowship.

↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:

– No

↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:

– No

Notes: Many times, the fellowship workers who take keen interest in the affairs of the group take the duty of succession serious and are usually involved in the process than those who just casually identify with the group.

↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:

– Yes

Notes: The group prays before embarking on the process of leadership change.

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

Notes: The group holds that all humans including their leaders are fallible. They however do not frivolously charge their leaders with such accusations.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– No

Notes: Followers seldom, if ever accuse their leaders of error though it is within their rights to do so if they feel the leaders have made mistakes in the discharge of their duties. Often times, there is a mechanism for resolving issues relating to mistakes made by the leaders without necessarily bringing accusations against the leaders.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– No

Notes: The group hardly has a tradition of accusing leaders of errors. If any act of the leaders is not acceptable to the followers, they tend to talk such over most times rather than resorting to accusations and acrimony.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– No

Notes: Political leaders do not interfere in the affairs of the group.

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Notes: Followers or disciples of the religious leader are not required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters. The obedience and submission of the followers to the leader is expected and in fact commanded by the supreme being. However, their obedience should not be a blind one. They are allowed to disagree with the leader in a bid to improve the outcomes of the group.

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: The group believes in the authority of the Protestant Holy Bible which consists of 39 Old Testament and 27 New testament books.

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: They are written and canonised

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

Notes: The scriptures is regarded as an inerrant and infallible word of God which never requires alteration.

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: The group relies on contributions from members of the fellowship, alumni, friends, patrons and churches favourably disposed to their efforts among students for building meeting centres in institutions of higher learning across the nation of Nigeria. However, there are very modest buildings erected at the National Camp grounds of the group in Kwali a town on the outskirts of Abuja, the Federal Capital Territory of Nigeria.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– No

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: The camp ground of the group is one such site dedicated to sacred practice (National

Convention and other religious meetings) among the people.

Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: Among the members of the group, the body and spirit/mind are conceived of as being distinct elements which make up the human body.

Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Other spirit-body relationship:

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that there is an afterlife at the close of this present dispensation. It is going to be a life earned on the basis of the kind of life each individual lives in this present life.

Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

Notes: The group points to the sky as the location of the afterlife for those who lived in accordance to divine instructions in this current life. They also speak of some space beneath the earth as the location of the afterlife for those who lived in disobedience to divine mandate in the current life.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Notes: The group does not believe in the reality or existence of reincarnation.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Notes: The group does not carry out burials for deceased members. This is because members are usually young adults. Deaths do not usually occur among them. When death does occur, it is the responsibility of the religious groups members belong to out of the campus to carry out or coordinate such burial though NIFES would send representatives to such burial.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: The group does not believe in the concept of co-sacrifices.

Are grave goods present:

– No

Notes: The group does not believe in the concept of grave goods

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: Formal burials are present but the group does not coordinate such burials. They only attend and may be given roles to perform at such occasions at the pleasure of the coordinating group which the member belongs to outside the campus. This is in most cases the family church of such members.

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

Notes: The group is not involved in warfare where members die in battles for which ceremonial burials are carried out outside the battle field when corpses are not retrievable. However, there have been some occasions when Christian students have been victims of violent attacks by religious fanatics from other faiths. The erection of cenotaphs however, does not apply to the group.

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: The choice of burial site for corpses of deceased members is at the discretion of the family.

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

Notes: The choice of burial site for corpses of deceased members is at the discretion of the family.

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

Notes: This is not usually practiced among the people. Burying corpses of young adults around family homes is not a common practice in many parts of the country. This is because many tribes in the country are usually pained by the sudden death of young folks and want to bury their corpses far away from the home so they do not continue to grieve each time they behold the tomb.

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes in the existence of supernatural beings.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: The group speaks of their supreme high god as one who possesses human qualities. He is said to possess a hand, eyes, arms, legs and other human emotions.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that the supreme high god lives in heaven above.

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

Notes: The group does not equate the supreme high god with any mortal being no matter how elevated the mortal is.

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

Notes: The monarch is not seen any more as an emanation of the supreme high God above other humans. The group accepts that all humans are made in the image and likeness of the supreme being.

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

Notes: The group holds that the supreme high god is completely good. They believe that evil can never be found in him.

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: They hold that the supreme high god is all powerful and benevolent.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that the supreme high god has all knowledge of the world. This is because they hold that the world is his creation and the work of his hands. As the framer of the world, they hold that there is nothing he does not know about the world.

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Notes: The group holds that the supreme high God's knowledge is not restricted to a particular domain of human affairs. He is supremely in charge of all that transpires in the universe. Therefore nothing that happens in the world happens without His permission.

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Notes: The group holds that the supreme high God can see what happens both in the dark and the open. Nothing is hidden from him.

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Notes: The group holds true the biblical saying in Psalms 139 that darkness is as light before the supreme high God. The members do not hide under the dark to perform any un toward act because they hold this belief to be true.

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that there is nothing hidden that the supreme high god cannot see and know.

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Notes: The group holds that the high God knows the real character of each human being. No one can hide their real personality from Him because He has every power to know the real essence of each individual.

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: The group holds that the supreme high god has knowledge of all things. They believe that he holds records of all that has ever happened in history. They also believe that he knows everything happening presently and is aware of all things that will happen in the future.

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

–Yes [specify]: The church holds that all knowledge (the ones known and unknown to men) resides with and emanates from the supreme high god.

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: The group holds that the supreme being is the cause of all actions and events on the earth. They belief that His will (either permissive or perfect will) makes all things come to pass. Nothing happens without his knowledge and permission.

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

Notes: The group holds that the supreme high god rewards all actions and thoughts of men. This includes those that are even hidden from other men.

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

Notes: The group holds that the supreme high god punishes all actions and thoughts of men. This includes those that are even hidden from other men.

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: The group holds that the supreme high god can choose to directly bring about a course of action in the world. They also hold that he can choose to cause such actions to happen by using other means or beings.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Since he is superbly good, the group believes that the supreme high god exhibits positive emotions.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: The group also holds that the supreme high god exhibits negative emotions when it becomes necessary to punish, avenge or reprimand evil doers of their works. This usually happens when such evil doers have been given enough opportunity to repent and turn from their wicked ways.

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– Yes

Notes: Though according to the group, the supreme high god does not possess hunger for food and other sensual things, he however possesses hunger to reward both the good and punish the evil actions of human.

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

Notes: The supreme high god does not permit this because he is a jealous god who never tolerates the idea of sharing his position or glory with other lesser beings.

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: The group holds that the supreme high god is all knowing, slow to anger and swift to forgive when humans turn away from and forsake their evil deeds.

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

Notes: The group holds that the supreme high God is willing to guide, lead and communicate with the living everyday.

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

Notes: The form of divination the group accepts and practices with the supreme high god is through prayers and seeking the high god through reading his word (the bible). He is said to speak to the current situations of Christians as they settle to read and meditate on the words written in the bible.

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: The supreme high god is said to communicate with group members through their circumstances, nature etc

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– No

Notes: The group beliefs that it is appointed to man to die once. After death, they acknowledge that there would be eschaton, a time for judgement which signals the eternal fate of each mortal. Spirits are held to vacate the realm of human existence once the body they occupied ceases to exist.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– No

Notes: They are not usually seen with the human eyes.

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: They believe that they have as much knowledge of the world as they are granted by the supreme high god whom they work with and represent in his theocratic government.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Notes: The group holds that Non-human supernatural beings have causal efficacy in the world as much as the supreme being grants them leave.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that Non-human supernatural beings could set machinery in motion to bring about a cause of action in the world without being directly involved in the actions.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

Notes: It is important to be clear about the kind of hunger these supernatural beings possess. It is not the hunger for food or drinks but the hunger to keep the world in order and reward good as they punish evil.

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: They possess or exhibit all features the supreme being needs of them to carry on with order in the world of humans.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– No

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

↳ Food:

– No

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

Notes: Although the group believes that her members should be perfect in their conduct everywhere, they place special emphasis on respecting sacred ground like the church auditoriums and other places of worship. They expect members to specially comport themselves well in such spaces so not to incur the wrath of the supreme being.

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

Notes: The group does not expect members to treat sacred objects like the bible with disdain.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: The group believes that the Christian life is a whole construct. They hold that the supreme being cares about every segment/aspect of the lives of a true Christian.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

↳ Incest:

– Yes

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: The group holds that the supernatural being cares about all forms of sexual involvements of their members. They hold that sex should be within the confines of marriage and it should be between heterosexual couples.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: The group holds that the supernatural being cares about every aspect of the lives of humans. This includes the desire to know and please him more, desire for acquisition of knowledge, justice and fairness etc.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that supernatural punishments are done through other entities like the elements of nature, natural phenomenon (eg) fire etc

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural punishments are meted out to enforce justice and fairness

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: The group holds that punishment in the afterlife entails eternal separation from the supreme high God. This means that there is no chance of redemption for the those who will be so punished.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

Notes: The group holds that the supreme beings detest evil and iniquity. They hold that God's eyes are too holy to behold iniquity. In fact, they align with the scriptures which says ... "all workers of iniquity shall be scattered" Psalms 92:9. As such, when iniquity is found in an individual, the group holds that God withdraws from them leaving them to all manners of evil including bad luck.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– Yes

Notes: Though the group does not involve in physical battles, they hold that life itself is a constant battle. As humans live daily they are bound to encounter different forms of challenges. When confronted by such battles without the support of the supreme being, humans are bound to fail and be defeated.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: Depending on the severity of offense, the group holds that humans suffer varying degrees of displeasure. While some may be subject to mild sensory displeasure, other suffer to the extreme.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:
– Yes

↳ Other [specify]
– Yes

Notes: The group holds that punishment in this life are quite diverse and at times countless. Humans may suffer punishments which include irreparable damages to their property, physical impairment, mental imbalance etc

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:
– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:
– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:
– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:
– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:
– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
– Yes

↳ Done randomly:
– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– Yes

Notes: The group holds that those who will be rewarded with rewards in the afterlife with the supreme being will be like the angels. They will take up an incorruptible form or shape.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– Yes

Notes: Though the form of existence in the afterlife cannot be strictly classified as reincarnation but those who will partake of the reward in afterlife according to the belief of the group will be in a superior realm of existence in heaven.

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - Yes

Notes: The group holds that rewards in this life consists of long life, peace within and around those who live according to divine command etc

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes in Jesus the Christ (messiah).

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– Yes

Notes: The group believes Christ is in heaven preparing homes for his human followers.

↳ Alive, identified:

– Yes

↳ Coming in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Coming on specified date:

– No

↳ Coming in unspecified time in near future:

– Yes

↳ Coming in unspecified time in distant future:

– No

↳ Coming has already passed:

– No

Notes: The group believes the messiah's work is at least two fold. He is reputed to have come earlier for the first part of his work (to save humankind from sin). He is expected to return to take his followers to a place where he is currently preparing for them in his kingdom.

↳ One in a line of many past and future messiahs:

– No

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– No

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– Yes

↳ Other purpose:

– Yes [specify]: The group believes that the messiah came to reconcile humans to God.

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at some other time:

– No

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes their members need to keep preaching about the coming kingdom to those who have not embraced Christ and so cause the good news of the kingdom to be known everywhere. It is after the preaching of the gospel across the world that the world will come to an end.

↳ Divine judgment event:

– Yes

↳ Restoration of the world:

– Yes

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:

– No

↳ Establishment of a new political system:

– No

↳ Establishment of a new religious system:

– Yes

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:

– Yes

↳ All religious in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– No

↳ A subset of religion in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– Yes

↳ All members of the sample region will survive the eschaton:

– No

↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton:

– No

↳ Other survival condition:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):

– Yes

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Yes

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

↳ Cooperation:

– Yes

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– Yes

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Yes

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– Yes

↳ Strength (physical):

– Yes

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– No

Notes: The group does not place premium on power, status and nobility.

↳ Humility / modesty:

– Yes

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– Yes

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:

– Yes

↳ Optimism / hope:

– Yes

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– Yes

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– Yes

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– Yes

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– Yes

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– No

Notes: The group admonishes members to place less importance on beauty and attractiveness but to have much of value hard work and respect for elders.

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– Yes

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes [specify]: Several other virtues are upheld by group. These include; hatred, empathy etc

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males):

– Yes

Notes: Though most members of the fellowship are young adults who are still singles, the group teaches its members that Christian marriage is between a male and female adult.

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: Members are taught to abstain from sexual relations with animals and people of same sex.

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Notes: Members are taught to abstain from sexual relations with animals and people of same sex

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

Notes: Members are taught to give of their valuable items to God who gave it to them in the first place. They are taught that He is also able to bless them more in several folds when they give back to him, to their fellow members and others outside the fellowship.

↳ To other in-group members:

– Yes

↳ To out-groups:

– Yes

↳ Destroyed:

– No

↳ Other:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Hours: 12

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Number of participants: 200

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Average interval [hours]: 48

Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– No

Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– No

Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– No

Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– No

Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Notes: The group at individual campus level takes care of members who need relief materials from time to time. This includes food, clothes and other necessities of life.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– I don't know

Notes: There are no elderly people among the group members. The group is comprised only of young adults and a few middle aged folks.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: There are no elderly people among the group members. The group is comprised only of young adults and a few middle aged folks.

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Notes: They operate within educational institutions not as education providers but support the spiritual needs of the members.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: The group's adherents interact with the bureaucracy in their school and other bureaucratic institutions of the government.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: This is provided by the authority of the educational institutions in some cases and by the government in other cases.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Private investors provide transportation for members across many of the campuses. However, in a few of the institutions, there exist isolated efforts by the school management and the government to provide transportation infrastructure

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Notes: The group encourages members to pay tithes in order to fulfil the group obligations.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Since most of the members are students, they are excluded from paying tax.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The group members interact with the nation's Police.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The group's members interact with the nation's judicial system.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Notes: The religious group does not enforce institutionalised punishment.

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The group members are subject to the nation's judicial system and could be sanctioned by the nation if they are found to have done wrong. However, the members are noted to exercise a high degree of compliance with the nation's legal code so that they do not often fall under the punishment of the State.

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Notes: Punishment for grave offenses could include execution

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Notes: This may apply if there are incontrovertible evidence that such property was obtained fraudulently or that they are proceeds of crime.

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: This depends on the personal choices of members. The group does not interfere with their choice to participate in the institutionalised military of their country.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The English language is the mode of communication in the group's meetings and other formal engagements.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: The group uses the Gregorian calendar in planning and executing their programmes.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The group uses the Gregorian calendar

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No